

4. Agroforestry & Enhanced Conditionality

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EURAF is an NGO, established in Paris on 16/11/2012, with a French Registration number of [W343014937](#) and a Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#). It aims “to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms”. It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries.

We review the proposed rules for "enhanced conditionality" in the new CAP and recommend: a) Member States should recognise the potential for agroforestry to contribute to all ten Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions, and include this in their GAEC guidance rules to farmers; b) "Hectares of Agroforestry" should count fully towards GAEC 9 whether the trees are on arable land, permanent grassland or permanent crops (this is not currently the case), and whether or not they have been assisted by current or previous Pillar II schemes; c) Member States should have flexibility over the permitted dimensions of Landscape Features (up to certain maxima - e.g. 20m hedge with), but the dimension should be clear to farmers, and the full GAEC9 area should be eligible to receive Direct Payments

1 What's new about "Enhanced Conditionality"?

Enhanced Conditionality will apply to all farmers in the new CAP, and combines the existing Cross-Compliance Rules with parts of the existing Greening Rules (Figure 1). It comprises 16 Statutory Management Requirements (SMRs) and 10 Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs).

Figure 1: Comparison of the CAP's current and proposed new green architecture

The June 2020 AgFish meeting of agricultural ministers requested several changes to GAEC wording (Table1).

Table 1. Amendments proposed to the wording of Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions

GAEC	Commission proposal (June 2018).	AgFish Council Proposal (June 2020) - for GAEC9 modified by the September 2020 meeting (<i>italics</i>)
1	Maintenance of permanent grassland based on a ratio of permanent grassland in relation to agricultural area.	Maintenance of permanent grassland based on a ratio of permanent grassland in relation to agricultural area at national, regional, sub-regional, group-of-holdings or holding level. This ratio shall not decrease by more than 5% compared to the reference year 2015.
2	Appropriate protection of wetland and peatland.	Appropriate Minimum protection of wetland and peatland at the latest by 2024.
3	Ban on burning arable stubble, except for plant health reasons	Unchanged
4	Establishment of buffer strips along water courses	Unchanged
5	Use of the Farm Sustainability Tool for Nutrients	Deleted - Moved to farm advisory services
6	Tillage management reducing the risk of soil degradation, including slope consideration	Tillage management or other appropriate cultivation techniques to limit the risk of soil degradation, taking into account the slope gradient
7	No bare soil in sensitive period(s)	Minimum soil cover in period(s) and areas that are most sensitive period(s).
8	Crop rotation	Crop rotation or other practices aiming at preserving the soil potential, such as crop diversification.
9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum share of agricultural area devoted to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimum share x% of arable land devoted to:(i)

	non-productive features or areas <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Retention of landscape features ● Ban on cutting hedges and trees during the bird breeding and rearing season ● As an option, measures for avoiding invasive plant species 	non-productive <i>areas and</i> features or (ii) catch crops or nitrogen fixing crops, cultivated without plant protection products. <i>For MS using only non-productive areas and features the minimum share is 3%. For catch crops a weighting factor of 0.3 is to be used</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Retention of landscape features ● Ban on cutting hedges and trees during the bird breeding and rearing season ● As an option, measures for avoiding invasive plant species
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Agroforestry has a large potential contribution to all ten GAEC conditions:

- **GAEC 1** (*Maintain permanent grassland*): silvopastoral systems adding value to “permanent grassland”, and provide animal welfare (shelter, forage), timber and flood control.
- **GAEC 2** (*Protection of peatland and wetland*): wetland agroforestry involving “swales (ditches) and berms (ridges) give new options for control of flooding in the lowlands.
- **GAEC 3** (*Maintenance of soil organic matter through a ban on burning stubble*): tree roots, branches and leaves significantly increase soil organic matter, and can do so at depth.
- **GAEC 4** (*Establish buffer strips along water courses*): planting trees in buffer strips improves nutrient filtration, and can be designed intelligently using the Farm Sustainability Tool using soil nutrient models.
- **GAEC 5**¹ (*Farm Sustainability Tool - FaST*): the FaST tool is designed to predict farm and plot scale nutrient fluxes - it should be extended to model the effect of trees in agroforestry and landscape features on nutrient and carbon storage.
- **GAEC 6** (Tillage management to limit degradation): silvoarable systems integrate well with cover crops, contour ploughing and no till systems.
- **GAEC 7** (No bare soil in sensitive periods): tree strips and cover crops limit wind or water erosion from bare soils.
- **GAEC 8** (Crop rotation - preserve the soil potential). Silvoarable systems with alleys adapted to standard machinery widths can be used in conventional crop rotations.
- **GAEC 9**² (Maintain “landscape and non-productive features”). Agroforestry lines and tree-landscape-features can be classed as “non-productive features” and will contribute to the national % GAEC thresholds.
- **GAEC 10** (Ban on planting or converting Natura 2000 sites): small-scale agroforestation using native species would be less destructive than afforestation with non-native species.

2 What is the argument about GAEC-9?

The EU Biodiversity Strategy advocates that at least 10% of “Agricultural Area³” should be used for “*high diversity landscape features*” In the draft Strategic Plan Regulation this area is referred to as “*GAEC9 - A minimum share of agricultural area devoted to non-productive features or areas*”. More recently the Commission has started calling the area “*Landscape Features and Rotational and Non-Rotational Set-aside*”, harking back to the CAP of 1992.

The governments of France, Spain and Germany refer to GAEC9 as “Areas of Ecological Interest” (AEI) [1,2]. **AEI is a term favoured by EURAF since it avoids the cumbersome wording of “non-productive features or areas” and the strange concept, introduced by the Biodiversity Strategy, of “non-productive trees”.**

Whatever the name, there is an understandable desire in the Commission to avoid the dilution of environmental ambition evident in the current CAP, where the “greening” area was reduced from 7% to 5% during dialogue discussions, restricted only

¹ Moved to the Horizontal “Farm Advisory and Knowledge Services” by the Council of Agric Ministers.

² This includes “*non-productive areas*” together with the “*landscape-features*” described in the current GAEC-7 i.e. “*Retention of landscape features, including where appropriate, hedges, ponds, ditches, trees in line, in group or isolated, field margins and terraces, and including a ban on cutting hedges and trees during the bird breeding and rearing season and, as an option, measures for avoiding invasive plant species*”.

³ Early drafts of the Biodiversity Strategy talked of “Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA)” but the final draft uses the term “Agricultural Area (AA)”. UAA comprises arable land, permanent grassland, permanent crops and kitchen gardens; whereas, AA includes UAA plus “unutilised agricultural area” and “special holding areas”. It excludes wooded area and other land occupied by buildings, farmyards tracks, ponds, scrubland etc (ref). In 2010 (ref) the Commission estimated that there were 11 million ha of abandoned agricultural land in the EU, or 5.2% of total Agricultural Area (AA). A further 20 million ha of agricultural land is estimated by the EU-JRC to be under “high potential risk” of abandonment by 2030 (ref).

to arable areas, and radically changed by the inclusion of catch-crops and N-fixing crops, which are generally accepted to make only small contributions to biodiversity [3–6].

DGENVI (e.g. [presentation on the Biodiversity Strategy, September 2020](#)) continue to stress that a 10% level for “Landscape Features and Set Aside” is needed to restore biodiversity lost in agro-ecosystems. In their words:

- *Huge areas of landscape features have been lost in the EU in the past decades due to land consolidation and intensification of farming (e.g. the French Agricultural Research Institute INRA estimated that no fewer than 350,000 hectares of hedges and trees on agricultural land disappeared between 1960 and 1990 in France, which is equivalent to 700,000 km of hedges, 17.5 times the earth's circumference, just for France.)*
- *There is broad evidence from a large number of studies that a minimum of non-productive areas and landscape features between 10 and 20% is required to halt and reinstall biodiversity loss in agriculture. **10% is at the bottom end of this range and is the absolute minimum of what is needed.***
- *The 10% target builds on the target of 7% proposed by the Commission for the CAP 2014-2020. In the legislative process, this was lowered down to 5% and productive land use was allowed to count to the target.*
- *Set-aside in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was introduced in 1992 as a tool to increase agricultural prices and farmers' income. It has been recognised that set-aside delivered major environmental benefits for biodiversity and has the potential for doing this even more if better targeted.*
- *The 10% target is ambitious, but it is absolutely feasible: Significant positive feedback on production will improve yields via better biological pest control, pollination, and climate adaptation benefits. Increased yields can offset setting aside of 8% of arable land*
- *The impact assessment for the CAP 2014-2020 assessed a scenario with a target of 10% ecological set-aside, which was found to have moderate economic effects* The focus can be on low-productivity land, so that the loss of agricultural production is much less than the share of land put aside. There is no requirement of having the target achieved on each farm. A 10% target would entail an economic loss of -1.7% compared to a 5% target. Positive feedback was not assessed.*

However the 3/9/2020 “[background note](#)” from the German Presidency of the AgFish Council says:

“... that the GAEC9 minimum percentage should be increased from 5% (as in the current greening) to [x]% with reference to arable land. As it was strongly required by many Member States, it should be possible to count certain productive uses against the minimum share. For catch crops (and only for those), a weighting factor of 0.3 is proposed. For those Member States who wish to count exclusively non-productive areas and features against the minimum share, a lower minimum share (3%) could be envisaged.”

The Commission have listed “hectares of agroforestry” as a “productive feature” (Table 1)

Table 1 - Productive and Non Productive EFA Types in the Staff Working Paper on the implementation of the EFA obligation under direct payments [7].

Productive EFAs	Non-productive EFAs
Hectares of agro-forestry	Land lying fallow
Strips along forest edges with production	Terraces
Short rotation coppice	Landscape features (hedges/wooded strips, isolated trees, trees in line, trees in group/field copses, field margins, ponds, ditches, traditional stone walls, other landscape features undercross-compliance)
Catch crops/green cover	Buffer strips
Nitrogen-fixing crops	Strips along forest edges without production

3 What are the EURAF Recommendations?

EURAF has three recommendations regarding Enhanced Conditionality and the inclusion of agroforestry in the new Areas of Ecological Interest (AEI - i.e. GAEC9):

- ecosystem services and biodiversity from ecological focus areas. *Ecol Indic.* 2016;69: 859–872.
6. European Commission. Commission Staff Working Document - Review of greening after one year. 2016 Jun. Report No.: SWD(2016) 218 final.
 7. European Commission. Implementation of the Ecological Focus Area obligation under the direct payment scheme. 2017. Report No.: Staff Working Document 121 Final. Available: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:c3cb70a2-146d-11e7-808e-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_3&format=PDF